

CURVATURE MEASUREMENTS OF NON-SYMMETRIC LAMINATES USING IMAGE PROCESSING

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SUMMARY: Manufacturing induced thermal residual stresses are always present in laminated polymeric composites and may affect both the strength and the elastic behavior of the structure. The idea of tailoring the thermal residual stresses to enhance the structural response of composite structures has been proposed in the literature. However, the practical implementation of this concept depends on the ability of accurately predicting the distribution of the residual stresses. The study of the variation of the curvature of non-symmetric laminates with temperature provides a measure of the magnitude of the thermal stresses and the mechanical behavior of the material with temperature. In this work, an experimental method based on the use of a digital camera and image processing techniques is proposed to perform such measurements. Experimental and FEM results for flexural curvatures are compared and a discussion on the design reference temperature is carried-out.

KEYWORDS: thermal stresses, reference temperature, curvature measurement, image processing, digital camera imaging, viscoelasticity, finite element, non-symmetric laminates.

INTRODUCTION

Due to the mismatch in the thermal properties of the constituents, manufacturing residual stresses are always present in laminated polymeric composites and may affect both the strength and the elastic behavior of the structure. Almeida and Hansen introduced the idea of tailoring the thermal residual stresses to enhance the structural response of composite structures. They demonstrated numerically that the buckling load [1] and natural frequencies [2] of composite plates with stiffeners could be very substantially affected by the thermal stress-resultants. However, the practical implementation of this design concept depends on the ability of accurately predict the distribution of the residual stresses.

As a result of the unbalanced thermal shrinkage across the laminate thickness, thin non-symmetrical laminates show notable curvatures as they cool from the processing to the room temperature. The magnitude of the induced residual stresses and the mechanical behavior of the material with temperature may be indirectly characterized by measuring the laminate curvatures. This particular feature of the thermo-mechanical behavior of non-symmetrical laminate is used to advantage in this work to evaluate the process induced residual stresses.

Several approaches have been used by many researches to obtain the cured shapes of non-symmetrical composite laminates. Height and length gages, traveling microscopes and profile

projectors are some of the tools reported in the literature [3 - 9]; even steel rules and a piece of paper and a pencil to trace the shape are referred [10, 11]. Nowadays, optical methods play an important role in experimental mechanics. The shadow Moiré technique to measure out-of-plane displacements in non-symmetrical laminates is described in [12 - 15]. A digital imaging technique, applicable to the spring-in problem associated with curing process, is presented in [16]. It was found by the authors of this article that there is a lack of work reporting results on measurements of laminates curvatures at temperatures above the room temperature. Only two works were found in the literature survey report this type of measurement. Strain-gages were used to estimate the curvature during heating and cooling of non-symmetrical specimens in [17] and [18] reports a measurement apparatus in which LVDTs (Linear Variable Differential Transformer) capture the displacements of specimens inside an oven.

Two different shapes of specimens are used in the experiments reported in the literature: square plates and laminate strips. Cutting a narrow strip of a cross-ply laminate along one of the two principal directions yields the flexural curvature along this direction. If now the cut is made diagonal, the strip presents the laminate torsional curvature, eventually combined with bending. It is important to remark that, in these experiments, the curvatures depend on the size and aspect ratio of the specimens.

In this work, an approach based on digital camera imaging technique is used for the experimental characterization of the variation of the curvature with temperature of non-symmetric cross-ply laminate samples. Images of the lateral view of narrow strip specimen within a climatic chamber may be taken by a digital camera through an existing window. The sample may be heated over a range of temperature yielding a collection of images that characterize the thermo-mechanical behavior of the sample. The acquired images are processed by specifically developed mathematical routines running in MATLAB[®], which improve the process of determination of the specimen flexural curvatures at a given temperature.

Since the problem is geometrically non-linear, a numerical model based on finite elements is used to model to the problem. The model assumes constant material properties and no viscoelastic effects. The concept of using the “stress-free temperature”, as proposed by Tsai [19], is discussed by comparing the experimental and simulation results.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Description of the Samples

The experiments were conducted using carbon/epoxy laminates due to their wide applicability in the aerospace industry. The material used is a pre-impregnated unidirectional tape Hexcel T7G190 with resin system F584 cured at 177 °C; the nominal thickness of each layer is 0.18 mm. The cure cycle applied was in conformance with the recommended manufacturer procedure. The laminates were produced by an aeronautic company with large experience in composite manufacturing. No post-cure process was carried out since it was not requested, neither recommended, by the prepreg manufacturer.

The square cured plates were trimmed by discarding a narrow 10 mm band along the edges. After that, the samples, in form of strips, were saw cut. All plates used in the experiments were manufactured from the same material batch and simultaneously cured. Different cross-ply stacking sequences were chosen: $[0_3/90_3]$, $[0_2/90_2]$, $[0/90]$, $[0_2/90]$ and $[0/90_2]$. These stacking sequences present significant curvatures at room temperature and the residual

stresses were found to be below the materials ultimate strength. Therefore, no cracks or any other type of irreversible damage were expected or found in the specimens.

The strips were 280 mm long and 12 mm wide. This aspect ratio approximates the samples to a beam rather than to a plate but it is sufficiently wide to provide adequate stability to the strip inside the climatic chamber.

In order to reduce the effects of the moisture absorption to a minimum, the strips were previously submitted to a drying process. This process was conducted according to ASTM D5229 [20] where the recommended temperature is established as 80 °C. The reference time period is a function of the resin moisture diffusivity constant; the sample is considered dry when the moisture content of the material changes by less than 0.01% within the reference time period. The oven-dry process was conducted for all the strips to be tested. No desiccators were used since the dry strips were always moved directly from the oven to the climatic chamber.

Experiment Set-up

A flat base plate was used to support the cross-ply laminates strips during test. Two reference marks were traced in the base plate in such way that they were always captured together in the images. Since the distance between the reference marks is known, it was possible to calibrate the measured values in pixels. Attached to the base plate, and in the background of the strip, a white painted plate provided a contrast to the acquired images and protected the sample from the chamber hot air flow. In order to avoid any undesirable motion of the sample, one of the sample edges was taped to the base plate whereas the opposite edge was allowed to slide over a smooth surface coated with a kapton tape to decrease the friction between the sample and the base plate. By doing that, it is assumed that the influence of the test device on the results is minimum. Fig. 1 depicts a sample and the described test device.

Fig. 1: Cross-ply sample and test device.

Fig. 2: Experiment set-up.

The dry sample was then placed inside a climatic chamber in the Laboratory of Integration and Test (LIT) at the Brazilian National Institute for Space Research (INPE). The chamber is able to either heat or cool the specimens, within tolerances of ± 1.0 °C while controlling the environment humidity. A digital camera, set to acquire images with 640 versus 480 pixels resolution, was placed in front of the climatic chamber existing window in such way that an aligned view of the sample could be captured by the camera and acquired by the computer. A lamp inside the chamber guarantees that the strip was properly illuminated. The temperature

was measured by a resistance thermometer placed near the sample. The experiment set-up is shown in Fig. 2.

Investigation of Creep Effects

In the experiments performed a temperature variation implies in a stress change. Since the samples are cross-ply laminates, the material viscoelasticity may manifest in the form of creep under constant or varying load. Modeling of this effect is quite complex due to the variation of the viscoelastic parameters with temperature. In order to experimentally characterize the creep effects and establish appropriate experimental procedures, creep investigations were carried-out previously to the actual temperature-curvature experiments. Creep depends primarily on the resin properties, on the degree of cure and on the level of stress to which the material is subjected. As all samples are from the same material and come from the same manufacturing batch, one can assume that the specimens with the largest residual stress correspond to the worst creep scenario. The Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) indicates the $0_2/90$ or the $0/90_2$ specimens are the most prone to creep effects. Shape measurements of the dry samples were made for creep investigations at a temperature of 80°C . This temperature is the upper limit established by the FAA (USA Federal Aviation Administration) for aeronautical structural analysis purposes. During the experiment, no control for humidity in the climatic chamber was used.

Experiment Description

The shape measurements were made from 20°C to 80°C in steps of 15°C for the curvature-temperature experiments. The dwelling time at each temperature before acquiring the image was determined from the creep investigations. A heating rate of 4°C per minute was used between the measurement temperatures and no humidity control of the climatic chamber was used. An image was acquired at each temperature step only during the heat-up phase of the specimens. Only one sample of each different type of laminate was tested. Three test runs were performed for each sample. Fig. 3 presents typical images for two different temperatures. The horizontal lines in the images are the climatic chamber window heaters.

Fig. 3: Images from the same sample at two different temperatures (left: 20°C , right: 80°C).

Data Processing

The images were processed in specifically developed mathematical routines running in MATLAB[®] to improve the determination process of the flexural curvature. Microsoft Paint[®] was used to select the region of interest in the original images before processing with the MATLAB[®] routines.

In the MATLAB[®], initially an approximation of the image is carried-out and used as reference for deletion of spurious points. By doing that, the horizontal lines from the window heaters and any undesirable spots were suppressed. The suppressed points are quantified to the user as output of the developed software. The specimen shape for all experiments was determined to be a nearly perfect arc of circle. The specimen shape only slight deviates from a circle for very thin specimens at temperatures close to the cure temperature; in this nearly flat

configuration, gravitational effects are important for thin specimens. Therefore, the least-squares method was applied to interpolate the remaining points and fit the best arc of circle to compute the radius of curvature and the error associated with it. At this point, the circle radius, and consequently the curvature, is defined in pixels and a dimensionalization is needed. An additional routine captures the reference marks traced on the test device base plate and calculates the multiplication factor to be applied to yield measurements in mm. A plot of the final curvature and of the valid and suppressed points allows a good visualization of the curve fit process.

The data processing and curvature determination process were validated by two independent means. First the routines results were compared with a Computer Aided Design (CAD) where the images were imported to the CAD environment and a circle was traced to fit the sample contour. Additionally, comparisons at room temperature were made with direct measurements of the height of samples laid over a flat table and assuming the length of the arc of the samples to be known. In both cases, there was excellent agreement between the different methods.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The dry-oven process was conducted to assess the required drying time for two different laminates: the six layers ($[0_3/90_3]$) and the two layer laminates ($[0/90]$). Three samples of each laminate were tested. The moisture equilibrium is reached between 12 to 14 hours for the thinner laminates and between 102 to 112 hours for the thicker laminates. The drying time was assumed conservatively to be five days at 80°C for all laminates, in spite of their different thicknesses. The mass change rates results for the oven-dry process assessment are shown in Fig. 4.

The creep investigations were performed for the $[0/90_2]$ laminate. Fig. 5 depicts the results. After a dwelling period of 30 minutes, the curvature does not show any significant changes and the resulting shape may be assumed to be that of steady state.

The flexural curvatures against temperature curves for the five different cross-ply laminates are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig.4: Mass change results.

Fig. 5: Creep investigations.

NUMERICAL SIMULATION

The curvature of non-symmetric laminates has been studied by many researchers in the last two decades. The problem is geometrically non-linear and the Kirchoff hypotheses apply. A geometrically non-linear finite element model that does not account either for viscoelastic effects or for the variation of material properties with temperature was used for comparison with the experimental results. Preliminary analysis results showed that the gravitational effects should be taken into account in the models, particularly for thin laminates. The models were built using the MSC NASTRAN[®]. The meshes were refined until reaching a convergence of less than 0.5 %, resulting in 1344 CQUAD4 laminated plate elements. The computation time for a full geometrically non-linear analysis with this mesh was acceptable using a standard personal computer. The elastic properties at RTD (room temperature - dry condition) were provided by the laminate manufacturer and are as follows:

$$E_1 = 130000 \text{ MPa} \quad E_2 = 9400 \text{ MPa} \quad G_{12} = 7200 \text{ MPa} \quad \nu_{12} = 0.27$$

where E_1 and E_2 are the modulus of elasticity in the fiber and transverse directions, respectively; G_{12} is the in-plane shear modulus and ν_{12} is the major Poisson ratio.

Measurement of the thermal expansion coefficients were not available and were assumed according to [21] as:

$$\alpha_1 = -0.9 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ \text{C} \quad \alpha_2 = 27 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ \text{C}$$

where α_1 and α_2 are the thermal expansion coefficients in the fiber and transverse directions, respectively.

DISCUSSIONS

Fig. 6 depicts the experimental and simulation results. For the $[0_3/90_3]$, $[0_2/90_2]$ and the $[0/90_2]$ laminates, in the range of temperature up to 80 °C, a linear interpolation fits the experiments results. In this case, the CLT could be used instead of the FEM results. For the others laminates, the non-linear finite element models should be used.

A shift between the experimental and simulation curves is observed for all laminates. This shift is a result of neglecting viscoelastic effects and the variation of mechanical and physical properties with temperature in the finite element model. It should also be noted that, for each laminate, this shift is constant within the test temperature range with excellent approximation. Therefore, the mathematical model neglecting the viscoelastic effects and assuming constant mechanical and physical properties may yield excellent agreement to the measured curvatures in the specified temperature range provided that an adequate correction is used. Also, it can be stated that the assumed elastic properties and thermal expansion coefficients are representative of the material behavior.

An excellent approximation between the curves is obtained by properly shifting the reference temperature. Fig. 6 includes the simulation adjusted to obtain the best fit to the experimental results. For each different laminate a different shift in the reference temperature applies indicating that the required change in the reference temperature depends on the laminate lay-up and thickness. Note that, the viscoelastic effects are accounted for during the experiments by the specified dwelling time between measurements.

These findings show that accurate results for the residual stresses may be obtained from simplified models (assuming constant material properties and no viscoelastic effects) if an “equivalent cure temperature” is used rather than the “stress-free temperature”, as suggested by Tsai [19]. The “stress-free temperature” is defined as the temperature at which the out-of-plane curvature of the laminate strip vanishes during heat-up. Fig. 6 presents the “equivalent cure temperatures” obtained for the tested laminates along with the corresponding standard deviations. The “equivalent cure temperatures” is between 157.1 and 178.4 °C for the tested laminates contrasting with the “stress-free temperature” which, in some cases, for thermoset composites, may be 30 °C below the cure temperature [19].

Fig. 6: Experimental, FEM and adjusted FEM curves for the 5 cross-ply laminates tested.

CONCLUSIONS

This work reports the development of a simple digital camera imaging technique to measure flexural curvatures of composite non-symmetric laminate strips within a range of temperature. The method uses either a climatic chamber or an oven with a window for obtaining the images. If proper illumination is used, the method is reliable, accurate and easy to implement. The process for determination of the curvatures is improved and automatized by using mathematical routines on the captured images, as done is this work with the MATLAB[®]. The method, when used to determine curvatures above room temperature, presents advantages when compared with any other alternatives, like strain-gages or the shadow Moiré. The proposed method measures the entire deformed shape of the specimen rather than the curvature at a certain point and is not affected by temperature.

Making use of the method, the experimentation findings indicate that an "equivalent cure temperature", determined by experiment, should be used instead of the "stress free temperature". Additionally, unlike the approach proposed in [19], the present method does not require heating the specimen above the glass transition temperature to estimate the equivalent cure temperature.

The establishment of the concept of the "equivalent cure temperature" represents a benefit on the composite laminate modeling and encourages the authors to extend this work to other types of laminates in a future work.

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